

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DDIA

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

ACADEMIC WRITING AT DOCTORAL LEVEL

1) INTRODUCTION

Taking graduate studies at the doctoral level is not an easy endeavor. However, EUCLID seems to have implemented the necessary strategies to make it as easy as possible for the student to navigate through, right from the start. Given that EUCLID's graduate programs are entirely online-based, and designed for a diverse international student body coming from a variety of educational systems, and professional backgrounds, one can understand why the University would put so much effort into ensuring that all the students acquire the skills necessary for undertaking such a project. All the graduate programs seem to start with the compulsory *ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate)* course, which takes students back to the very foundations of international academic writing while instilling the habits of writing excellence into each, to meet the doctoral level standard of perfection. In the subsequent sections of this paper, I will discuss and reflect on some of the key elements covered in period one (1) of the ACA-401D course, which is divided into seven periods in total, each containing a separate set of study materials, learning objectives and assignments.

2) BACK TO BASICS – TOOLS OF THE TRADE

The period one (1) study material comprises an 87-paged *ACA-401 Coursepack* document and a short 14-minute video *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Both the *Coursepack* and the video lesson take the student back to the basics of academic writing, besides serving as useful grammar refreshers. The video, moreover, is helping students unfamiliar with different preformatted styles within MS Word to learn to use EUCLID's prescribed

response paper template correctly. The instruction provided in the video is particularly significant since response papers represent an essential part of the assessment process and need to be written following the required rules and standards. The constant emphasis throughout the *Coursepack* is placed on different existing rules of writing to produce excellent and engaging content. However, the extreme importance of form is not left out either. On the contrary, given the doctoral level of studies' standard of excellence requirements, students are reminded that both the form and the content are crucial elements of success.

In my case, such order of things was particularly interesting and useful, having met in the past many fellow master students completing their studies while still trying to learn how to reference correctly and write academically, often by themselves. This specific issue made me wonder if EUCLID had the same insights about international students, which led to the implementation of this sequence of coursework in this study period. On the other hand, it also made sense, considering that many students may undertake doctoral studies many years after their undergraduate and graduate studies. By starting from the basics, the University ensures that everyone has the requisite skills to succeed.

Furthermore, I have noticed that the course consists of seven study periods, each with its own set of study materials. Although not very extensive, as one might expect at this level, the mandatory study material surprised me with the depth and detail into which it went, in an attempt to cover all the essentials.

a) Essay Writing and Researching

The first 45 pages of the *Coursepack* contain various essay writing rules and tips from several sources. The first five pages comprise *Essay Writing Basics* from the Writing Center of the University of New South Wales (UNSW). This section was particularly exciting for me to find being already familiar, as I have often referred to it in the past. As a teacher, I regularly share this particular guide with my students to help them improve their academic writing skills. However, the *Coursepack* document comes without a contents page, which made it a bit difficult to navigate through, or search and review particular materials or points. I thought that it would have been easier to have each document as separate study material, or have a table of contents added, to address this.

Moreover, I was also surprised that the *Essay Writing Basics* guide was included at the beginning of the doctoral academic writing course, making me question its necessity. I wondered if one can get accepted to doctoral studies without having completed an undergraduate or graduate program. If yes, how could they graduate without having mastered the basics of essay writing? Perhaps the reasoning was, as I have commented earlier in this paper, that many students join the doctoral program after many years away from academia, and such refresher then would make perfect sense to make sure they are ready for the journey.

b) Referencing and Plagiarism

Following the UNSW guide in the *Coursepack* is a titleless 37-slides' PowerPoint presentation, presumably authored by EUCLID. The presentation explains what an excellent paper should look like, how to use citations, avoid plagiarism, as well as how to produce writing that flows, and engages the reader. What comes next is a 3-page document titled *Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers*, that looked very familiar, and which contained 10-points or 'rules of thumb' (EUCLID 2015, 43-45). I find that it would have been more logical to start with the presentation that gives an introduction and overview of these particular issues and then follow with the *Essay* guide and the rest. The *Some Rules of Thumb* paper would have followed more logically the 5-paged UNSW guide *Essay Writing Basics*, as it essentially summarizes the slightly longer UNSW guide. In my opinion, the existing arrangement of the *Coursepack* material makes the reading and navigating it a bit confusing.

On the other hand, the presentation section, dealing with referencing and plagiarism, was particularly significant for me. Firstly, it has introduced me to Chicago (here referenced as *Turabian*) style, a new rule of style that I have not used previously, and which would require rereading and revisiting several times to master. In fact, as I was writing this paper, I had to remind myself to refer to the CMS *Crib Sheet* (EUCLID 2015, 66-77) which outlines the fundamental rules, and not to use the styles I am familiar with and used to but to ensure I am applying the new Chicago style. All in all, a handy reminder that learning is a never-ending process and that every new stage has its own rules and steps which a student must undergo and master in order to progress toward the final objective of obtaining the relevant degree.

In this section, very interesting and useful was the part in which different examples of how to paraphrase and summarize are given, and when to reference and when not to (EUCLID 2015, 29-30). We are also reminded that when using footnote referencing we should not add the "Works Cited/Reference" list at the end of our paper (EUCLID 2015, 37). Moreover, we are reminded that overuse of quotations is to be avoided, as it may give an impression that we have not done enough of our own research, and have instead overly relied on the works and words of others (EUCLID 2015, 22).. The importance of proper referencing in academic writing, clearly, cannot be overemphasized and bears repeating and reminding, such as when and how to use direct quotes, and the acceptable length of direct quotations and how to reference those as separate indented paragraphs using 'Quote Style' formatting in the EUCLID template (EUCLID 2015, 20), as opposed to shorter quotations which are incorporated within our own text with the use of quotation marks, and followed by the author's name and page number in parenthesis (EUCLID 2015, 19).

c) US vs. UK Spelling and Punctuation

The section on American vs. British spelling was particularly useful and informative. This section was and will continue to be helpful, as I switch between the two styles in my work (and other studies) and my doctoral studies at EUCLID, considering

that the University uses the US spelling as a rule while I have completed my previous studies in UK and EU universities. I have also realized that I need to pay attention not to mix the two styles, as it sometimes happens.

As I was studying this section, I have found out that under the influence of massive amounts of information that I consume daily over the years, I have inadvertently adopted many of the rules of the US spelling without even noticing. Going through the five pages of this section (54-59), I have been reminded of and have also learned some nuanced differences that I was not previously aware of, or have long forgotten, for different reasons.

Some examples are the differences in the formatting of dates and placement of periods, commas, and other punctuation marks in the two styles, where the US format places all punctuation within the closing quotation marks. In contrast, the UK puts the punctuation outside the quotation marks (59).

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, period one *Coursepack* represents a mix of documents from various sources, all addressing a variety of foundational requirements of academic writing. Having in mind the diversity of the EUCLID's student body, it is understandable and logical that the University would take such an approach to ensure that all students start from an equal footing. Regardless of their previous educational and professional backgrounds, and the years they took between their previous studies and their doctoral program with EUCLID, the courseworks takes students back to basics, through to the fine details of often omitted but important punctuation and grammar rules. While I have at times found some sections repetitive, such as essay writing rules (albeit coming from two different sources), on the whole, I can see myself going back to this particular coursepack as a useful and quick reference in the future.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack. Washington DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed April 27, 2020).

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.